

Research

Research on Digital Finance and Enterprise Investment Efficiency in Middel Eastern Companies

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Abstract: Investment plays a vital role in stimulating the GDP growth of Middel East countries (MEC) and is essential for promoting the country's economy towards high-quality development and the overall building of a socialist modernized nation. This article aims to analyze A-share listed firms from 2013 to 2022. The Richardson model use the absolute residual value derived from regression analysis to measure the degree of wasteful investment in firms. This number functions as a reverse indication of investment efficiency. This study expands upon the current empirical research on the economic results and factors that influence investment effectiveness in the realm of digital finance. This study provides actual proof that businesses may efficiently utilize the informational and resource benefits provided by digital finance to tackle investment efficiency problems.

Keywords: Digital finance; Investment efficiency; Middel East

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Introduction

At present, Middel East countries (MEC) economy has shifted from high-speed growth to high-quality development. In the process of optimizing the supply structure, it is necessary to fully leverage the role of investment, balance quality and efficiency, and shift economic growth from investment scale driven to investment efficiency driven. Enterprises are one of the most important market entities in the real economy, and their sustainable and stable development plays a crucial role in Middel East countries (MEC) economic and social development and progress. The healthy development of enterprises cannot be separated from effective investment, and investment activities are an important way for enterprises to create value. At present, the overall investment efficiency of listed companies in MEC is not high. On the one hand, due to the imperfect capital market and information asymmetry, some companies face serious financing constraints when external financing, unable to obtain sufficient funds in a timely manner, and are forced to give up good investment opportunities; On the other hand, due to the existence of principal-agent relationships, management may blindly invest in popular industries and carry out diversified operations for self-interest, rather than making investment decisions based on the principle of maximizing company value, leading to serious overinvestment problems

in some companies and reducing investment efficiency. Therefore, in the critical period of starting the comprehensive construction of a socialist modernized country, if the investment efficiency of listed companies in MEC cannot be effectively improved, it will inevitably have adverse effects on the high-quality development of enterprises of Middel East countries and even the entire economy and society.

2. Literature Review

The research on the impact of personal characteristics of managers on investment efficiency focuses on gender, age, education level, tenure, overseas experience, and manager overconfidence. When there is uncertainty in the future, they are more inclined to avoid risks rather than take risks, thus preventing inefficient investment by the company (Liu 2021). The longer a senior executive is in office, the more effective the team communication mechanism and information sharing can be promoted, so that executives do not overly rely on personal information when making investment decisions, make risky behaviors, improve the scientific of investment decisions, and thus suppress excessive investment by the enterprise (Gao 2020). A study proposed that good internal control can, on the one hand, make the information transmission and communication channels of enterprises smoother, and at the same time, improve the quality of the information transmitted, thereby reducing the asymmetry of internal and external information of the enterprise (Ruipeng 2019). Researchers found that in enterprises with high equity concentration, the interests of the enterprise and the major shareholders have a high degree of consistency, so the enterprise can make investment decisions more efficiently and avoid missing worthwhile investment opportunities due to tedious voting on investment matters and internal power balance issues (Monteiro 2021). The study shows that when a company has sufficient free cash flow, if the board of directors is large or there is a situation where the chairperson also serves as the general manager, managers will make excessive investments based on the surplus of free cash flow (Zhou 2020). Researchers believe that establishing an effective management incentive mechanism can reduce the inconsistency of interests between management and shareholders and reduce the underinvestment of enterprises caused by management negligence and risk reduction (Fu 2020) (Vargas 2020). Their findings indicate that in addition to mitigating financing constraints and exerting resource effects, financial technology can also decrease agency costs and exert governance effects. As a result, corporate investment efficiency is enhanced (Aggarwal 2006). As the industry enters its mature stage, risk will correspondingly diminish. This will mark a significant milestone in the evolution of fintech's influence on the investment efficiency of corporations (Beck 2018). The impact of digital finance development on technology-based enterprises was empirically examined by researchers. Technology-driven businesses are significantly reliant on external financing to invest in groundbreaking research initiatives (Benmelech 2010). Digital finance can increase the investment efficiency of technology-based businesses by facilitating the maintenance of adequate currency reserves, decreasing financing costs, and enhancing the efficiency of financial services. While it has the potential to mitigate underinvestment, it may also intensify overinvestment (Dolata, 2009). The amelioration of overinvestment is observed in small-scale enterprises, whereas the enhancement of underinvestment is primarily concentrated in the central and western regions.

3. Research Models and Variables

3.1 Research Model

This article establishes the following model to test the impact of digital finance on enterprise investment efficiency, where $Inv_{i,t}$ represents investment efficiency, $Dfi_{i,t}$ represents the level of digital finance development, and other variables are defined in the variable definition table.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Inv_{i,t} (Inv_{i,t}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 Dfi_{i,t} + \beta_2 Size_{i,t} + \beta_3 Lev_{i,t} + \beta_4 Roa_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_5 Growth_{i,t} + \beta_6 Ocf_{i,t} + \beta_7 Inddir_{i,t} + \beta_8 Dual_{i,t} + \beta_9 Top1_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_{10} Soe_{i,t} + \beta_{11} Age_{i,t} + \sum Year + \sum Ind + \varepsilon_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

3.2 Variable Definition

1. Measurement of Digital Finance

At present, there are three main methods for measuring digital finance: text mining, digital inclusive finance index, and the use of financial technology measurement indicators. The subjectivity of text mining methods is too strong, making it difficult to ensure the robustness of research results. Using financial technology indicators to measure is equivalent to equating financial technology with digital finance, but the two are not in the same relationship, so they are not accurate and comprehensive enough, it includes multiple dimensions such as coverage breadth and usage depth, considers the inclusiveness and technological attributes of digital finance, and provides a more comprehensive, objective, and accurate measurement of the development level of digital finance.

As a proxy variable, this article also uses this index to measure the level of digital finance development. In the core empirical part of this article, the digital financial development index is adopted based on the urban level caliber.

2. Measurement of Enterprise Investment Efficiency

At this time, the investment cash flow sensitivity model (FHP model), the cash flow and investment opportunity interaction discrimination model (Vogt model), and the residual measurement model (Biddle model and Richardson model) are the three predominant models used by academicians to assess investment efficiency. With respect to these three categories of measurement techniques, the residual model is the most prevalent. The paradigm proposed by Richardson (2006) is widely employed by academics to assess the investment efficiency of businesses. Consequently, this paradigm is also employed in this article to assess the investment efficiency of businesses. As determined by the model, the investment efficiency of businesses is denoted by the absolute value of the regression residual. As the degree of inefficient investment among enterprises increases with the absolute value of the regression residual, investment efficiency decreases and the regression residual value decreases. The enterprise achieves greater investment efficiency as the degree of inefficient investment decreases. This article utilizes the findings of Ma (2014) and Li (2009) to assess the expansion of businesses through the application of the revenue growth rate and Tobin Q value, respectively. By employing the Richardson model to perform regression and derive residual values, investment efficiency can be assessed in terms of the absolute residual value. The precise model is defined as follows:

$$\text{Invest}_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Invest}_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Size}_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 \text{Lev}_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 \text{Growth}_{i,t-1}(\text{TobinQ}) + \beta_5 \text{Age}_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 \text{Ret}_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 \text{Cash}_{i,t-1} + \sum \text{Industry} + \sum \text{Year} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

Among them: Invest represents the current investment scale of the enterprise, Size is the enterprise scale, Lev is the asset liability ratio, Growth is the growth rate of operating income, Tobin Q is the ratio of asset market value to replacement cost, Age is the enterprise age, Ret is the stock return rate, Cash is the cash asset status, and fixed effects of industry and time are considered. Table 1 defines all the variables.

Table 1 Variable Definitions

Variable category	Variable symbols	Variable Name	Variable definitions and calculation methods
Dependent variable	inv1	Investment efficiency	Measuring the growth of a company based on the growth rate of operating revenue, regressed using the Richardson (2006) model
	inv2	Investment efficiency	Measuring corporate growth using Tobin Q and regressing based on Richardson's (2006) model
Explanatory variables	dfi	Digital finance	Digital Inclusive Finance Index/1000
Mediating variables	kz	Financing constraints	KZ index
	riskt	Risk bearing level	The volatility of the return on total assets of enterprises
	mfee	Management expense rate	Management expenses/core business income

Control variable	size	Enterprise scale	Natural logarithm of total assets
	lev	Asset liability ratio	Total liabilities/total assets
	roa	Return on total assets	Net profit/total assets
	growth	Revenue growth rate	Growth in operating revenue/previous year's operating revenue
	ocf	Cash flow from operating activities	Net cash flow from operating activities/average total assets

4 Empirical Results Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistical results of the main variables in this article are shown in Table 2. From the table, the minimum, average, and maximum values of investment efficiency (inv1) are 0.000, 0.023, and 0.127, respectively, while the minimum, average, and maximum values of investment efficiency (inv2) are 0.000, 0.021, and 0.118, respectively. This indicates that there is a common situation of inefficient investment in Chinese enterprises, and the difference between the maximum and minimum values is significant, indicating that there is a significant difference in investment efficiency levels between different enterprises. From the perspective of digital finance, the maximum value is 0.322 and the minimum value is 0.057, indicating a significant difference in the development level of digital finance among different cities. However, the median is 0.233 and the average is 0.220, which is closer to the maximum value, indicating that the development level of digital finance in most regions is high. From the perspective of controlling variables, there is a significant difference between the maximum and minimum values, and there are significant differences in relevant indicators among different enterprises. To avoid the interference of these factors, it is necessary to control them.

Table 2 Descriptive statistical analysis of main variables

	N	Mean	St.Dev	min	Median	max
inv1	207	0.023	0.025	0	0.014	0.127
inv2	207	0.021	0.022	0	0.014	0.118
dfi	207	0.22	0.07	0.057	0.233	0.322
kz	207	1.099	2.322	-5.643	1.323	6.319
riskt	148	0.041	0.049	0.002	0.022	0.276
mfee	207	0.084	0.072	-0.076	0.068	0.423
size	207	22.358	1.295	20.057	22.167	26.359
lev	207	0.437	0.202	0.059	0.432	0.88
roa	207	0.036	0.059	-0.248	0.035	0.192
grow	207	0.153	0.378	-0.543	0.096	2.309
ocf	207	0.049	0.067	-0.149	0.048	0.242

4.2 Correlation Analysis

To ensure the robustness of the regression results obtained from the empirical model in the following text, it is necessary to ensure that the relevant variables do not directly have multicollinearity. Therefore, correlation analysis was conducted on the explanatory variable, dependent variable, and control variable to avoid serious collinearity affecting the regression results. Table 3 shows the Person correlation coefficients of each variable. Firstly, digital finance is significantly negatively correlated with the investment efficiency of enterprises at the 1% level, which preliminarily verifies the correctness of hypothesis H1 in this article, that is, digital finance can improve the investment efficiency of enterprises. However, the impact of digital finance on the efficiency of corporate investment may also be influenced by other factors, and further evidence is needed after adding control variables. Secondly, the data in the table shows that the investment efficiency of enterprises is significantly correlated with other control variables, indicating that the

selection of control variables is reasonable. Finally, the absolute values of the correlation coefficients in the table are mostly less than 0.5, all less than 0.8, indicating that there is no severe multicollinearity between the basic variables.

Table 3 Personal correlation analysis

	inv1	inv2	dfi	kz	riskt	mfee
inv1	1					
inv2	0.856***	1				
dfi	-0.217***	-0.119***	1			
kz	0.012*	-0.035***	-0.195***	1		
riskt	0.001	0	0.013	0.114***	1	
mfee	0.067***	0.072***	-0.151***	-0.033***	0.087***	1
size	-0.110***	-0.120***	0.107***	0.120***	-0.092***	-0.311***
lev	-0.056***	-0.082***	-0.065***	0.624***	0.013	-0.257***
roa	0.050***	0.054***	-0.040***	-0.503***	-0.248***	-0.102***
grow	0.053***	0.070***	-0.036***	-0.060***	-0.032***	-0.075***
ocf	0.059***	0.073***	0.070***	-0.588***	-0.076***	-0.102***

Note: * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.05

4.3 Analysis of Regression Results

This article uses a fixed effects model for regression analysis. Table 4 presents the results of the impact of digital finance on corporate investment efficiency. Columns (1) and (2) show the regression results of digital finance on investment efficiency without adding control variables. The regression coefficients of digital finance are -0.768 and -0.376, respectively, and they are significant at the 1% level. This indicates that digital finance can suppress inefficient investment by enterprises and improve investment efficiency, verifying hypothesis H1. Columns (3) and (4) represent the results after adding control variables and fixing the industry and time. The regression coefficients are still significantly negative, with values of -0.444 and -0.201, respectively. This once again proves that digital finance can have a positive effect on corporate investment efficiency, verifying hypothesis H1 in this paper.

Table 4 Regression results of the impact of digital finance on enterprise investment efficiency

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	inv1	inv2	inv1	inv2
dfi	-0.768*** (0.028)	-0.376*** (0.023)	-0.444*** (0.082)	-0.201*** (0.072)
size			-0.008*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)
lev			0.026** (0.011)	0.027*** (0.01)
roa			0.007 (0.032)	0.003 (0.03)
grow			0.034*** (0.005)	0.037*** (0.005)
ocf			0.135*** (0.026)	0.148*** (0.024)
r2	0.047	0.014	0.125	0.082

Note: * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.05

4. 4 Robustness Test

To account for endogenous processing, the instrument variable is the network penetration rate of each country, as obtained from the Statistical Report on MEC's Internet Development. The regression outcomes presented in Table 5 indicate a robust correlation between digital finance and Internet penetration. Furthermore, the analysis reveals the absence of any overidentification or weak instrumental variable issues, suggesting that the instrumental variable selection was effective. The regression coefficients associated with digital finance in the entire sample remain statistically negative at the 1% and 5% significance levels. This suggests that digital finance exerts a substantial impediment on enterprises' inefficient investment. This supports the article's H1 hypothesis even further.

Table 5 Robustness test

	(1) dfi	(2) inv1	(3) inv2
size	0.000 (0.000)	-0.007*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)
lev	0.002** (0.001)	0.023** (0.011)	0.027*** (0.010)
roa	0.008*** (0.002)	0.014 (0.032)	0.004 (0.030)
grow	0.000 (0.000)	0.034*** (0.005)	0.037*** (0.005)
ocf	-0.001 (0.002)	0.134*** (0.026)	0.148*** (0.024)
r2	0.944	0.121	0.082

Note: * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.05

5. Conclusion

Investment efficiency is vital to the growth of businesses and the economy. In the context of MEC's economic transition towards high-quality development, the rapid advancement of digital finance is contingent upon policy support and scientific and technological advancements. The advancement of digital finance has a substantial positive impact on the investment efficiency of businesses; that is, as digital finance development progresses, enterprise investment efficiency increases proportionally. Digital finance has two distinct effects: one is a resource effect, which facilitates the expansion of credit resources, enhances the accessibility of credit resources, and strengthens oversight and risk assessment of enterprises; the other is an information effect, which diminishes information asymmetry, improves the quality of enterprise information disclosure, decreases agency costs, and strengthens supervision and risk assessment of enterprises.

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